

FORMATION OF ENGINEERING THINKING IN THE MINDS OF YOUNG STUDENTS

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Annotation: In this article, the assessment of professional competence is based on the essence and characteristics of professional formation. The pedagogue's cognitive activity is largely determined by the complexity, dynamics, non-standardity of the things being studied, the influence of boundaries separating social phenomena, their search, uncertainty, which implies observation, the skill of modeling the inner world of the interlocutor. is considered as competence for a certain profession.

Key words: dynamics, non-standard, observability, competent, influence of boundaries, productive, creative, creative thinking, individual phenomenon.

Today's educational reforms are clearly targeted in our research. The relevance of our work is that in the globalized competitive age, we have a great goal to educate young people who can fully respond to the demands of tomorrow, productive and creative thinking, and to this end, we test a number of scientific research and new innovative methods through our own experiences. we have been using them in our educational process, distinguishing their shortcomings and positive aspects. Today's students of the 21st century, along with the development of time, the abundance of external information, in some sense, imposes a great responsibility on us researchers.

The strategic direction of the development of the education system in society is the intellectual and moral development of a person based on his purposeful independent activity in various fields. In our country, along with the developed

countries of the world, in the process of educational reforms, the promotion of independent education is an important task. The research of the phenomenon of education of the professional competence of the pedagogue is expressed in the works of a number of scientists. These authors put forward the opinion that together with the qualities of professional competence - reliability characterize the pedagogical culture of the teacher as a professional - individual phenomenon. In turn, the concept of professional competence, as stated by V.A. Slavenin, represents the unity of the theoretical and practical readiness of the pedagogue to carry out pedagogical activities and describes his professional formation.

Competence in higher education: spiritual, motivational, intellectual and practical self-development, volitional and emotional self-management. The student acquires methods of activity according to his personal interests and capabilities, which helps him to develop his personal qualities characteristic of a modern specialist, to form his thinking, culture and behavior.

The essence of the concept of "competence". In the conditions of market relations, resistance to strong competition, which takes priority in the labor market, requires every specialist to have professional competence and to improve it consistently. So, what is competence? What qualities are reflected on the basis of professional competence? It is necessary for a teacher to be able to highlight the qualities of competence. In this place, we will talk about these and related ideas. The English concept of "competence" literally means "ability". The content serves to illuminate "the effective use of theoretical knowledge in the activity, the ability to demonstrate high-level professional skills, skills and talents."

The concept of "competence" entered the field of education as a result of scientific research by psychologists. From a psychological point of view, competence is "how a specialist behaves in unconventional situations, unexpected situations, engages in communication, takes a new way in relations with opponents, performs ambiguous tasks, uses conflicting information, consistently develops and possessing a plan of action in complex processes.

Professional competence does not mean the acquisition of separate knowledge and skills by a specialist, but the acquisition of integrative knowledge and actions in each independent direction. Also, competence requires constant enrichment of professional knowledge, learning new information, understanding important social requirements, finding new information, processing it and being able to use it in one's work.

Professional competence is evident in the following cases:

- ✓ in complex processes;
- ✓ performing unclear tasks;
- ✓ using conflicting information;
- ✓ being able to have an action plan in an unexpected situation.

Specialist with professional competence:

- ✓ consistently enriches his knowledge;
- ✓ learns new information;
- ✓ deeply understands the requirements of the era;
- ✓ seeks new knowledge;

processes them and uses them effectively in his practical work.

Below, the essence of the qualities reflected on the basis of professional competence will be briefly explained.

1. Social competence - the ability to show activity in social relations, the ability to communicate with subjects in professional activities.
2. Special competence - preparation for organizing professional-pedagogical activity, rational solution of professional-pedagogical tasks, realistic assessment of activity results, consistent development of BKM, this competence is mainly psychological, methodical, informational, creative, innovative and communicative competence. is thrown to z. They represent the following content:

- 1) psychological competence - the ability to create a healthy psychological environment in the pedagogical process, to organize positive communication with students and other participants of the educational process, to understand and eliminate various negative psychological conflicts in a timely manner;
- 2) methodical competence - the methodical rational organization of the pedagogical process, the correct determination of the forms of educational or educational activity, the ability to choose methods and tools in accordance with the purpose, the ability to effectively use methods, the successful use of tools;
- 3) informational competence - searching, collecting, sorting, processing necessary, important, necessary, useful information in the information environment and using them purposefully, appropriately, effectively;
- 4) creative competence - critical and creative in relation to pedagogical activity approach, being able to demonstrate his creative skills;
- 5) innovative competence - putting forward new ideas on improving the pedagogical process, improving the quality of education, increasing the effectiveness of the educational process, and successfully implementing them into practice;
- 6) communicative competence - the ability to communicate sincerely with all participants of the educational process, including students, to be able to listen to them, to have a positive influence on them.
7. Personal competence - to consistently achieve professional growth, to increase the level of competence, to demonstrate one's internal capabilities in professional activity.
8. Technological competence - assimilation of advanced technologies that enrich professional-pedagogical BKM, ability to use modern tools, techniques and technologies.
9. Extreme competence - in emergency situations (natural disasters, technological process failure), rational decision-making and correct movement skills in case of pedagogical conflicts.

In the works of pedagogical scientists, various aspects and components that allow a wider and more detailed study of competence from a pedagogical point of view have been isolated and studied.

S.E. The following definitions of competence are given by Shishov:

- general competence based on acquired knowledge, experience, values and skills due to study;
- the ability to establish a connection between knowledge and situations, to find a suitable solution to the problem (it is permissible only if it is demonstrated in a certain situation to say that it is competence.

The formation of the professional competence of the future teacher of vocational education occupies a special place among the complex problems in the training of pedagogues. Especially at the current stage of reforms related to the modernization of education, the problem of adaptation to professional pedagogical activity is becoming more evident.

It is necessary to include the groups of diagnostic, communicative, management and projective studies in the essential characteristics of the professional competence diagnosis. The pedagogue's cognitive activity is largely determined by the complexity, dynamics, non-standardity of the things being studied, the influence of the boundaries that separate social phenomena, their search, uncertainty, which implies the skill of observation, modeling the interlocutor's inner world. In this case, the characteristics of self-regulation are characterized by the need to constantly improve one's knowledge and skills, and the ability to strictly coordinate one's behavior towards other people.

In the works dedicated to the research of the professional education of the teacher, it is distinguished by the following types:

- ability to be specially trained - having a sufficiently high level of professional activity, the ability to plan one's future professional development;

- ability of social upbringing - mastery of joint professional activity, cooperation, as well as the methods of professional communication adopted in this book, social responsibility for the results of one's professional profession.

The professional competence of the teacher of vocational education, willful qualities, intellectual potential, emotional qualities, practical skills, interrelation of self-management abilities and individual reflecting the level of socio-cultural activity of the person formed on the basis of qualities.

According to the tradition formed in European countries, the professional qualification is measured by the competence of the specialist, and the educational system aimed at its formation is measured by the level of knowledge, skills and qualifications.

The following can be recognized as important pedagogical conditions in the training of a teacher of vocational education:

- normative and educational-methodical documents that can meet modern requirements (state education standard, model curricula, working curricula, model curricula, working programs, textbooks, educational availability of manuals, methodological recommendations, additional special literature, instructional tools, lesson plans, projects, etc.);
- high level of knowledge, skills and qualifications of scientific pedagogical staff (professors, associate professors, teachers, qualified tutors, technical staff), sufficiently developed level of professional competence and having scientific potential;
- material and technical aspects of the educational process (educational buildings, educational auditoriums, educational workshops, practical laboratory equipment), information technologies (radio, television, computer, copiers, laboratory equipment) equipment, audio, video, multimedia, simulators, film projectors, slide projectors, video projectors, availability of a set of technical tools, etc.) are sufficiently provided;

- the creation of a socially and educationally-technologically favorable environment (teachers, students, leaders and students, as well as the content, direction, unity of goals, etc. of mutual relations of students);
- consistent, continuous and systematic implementation of organizational and educational-practical activities.

Summarizing the definitions and descriptions given to the concept of "teacher's professional competence", it can be interpreted as follows: Teacher's professional competence is one of the important aspects of professional competence in the work of a pedagogue is one, and represents all the needs, abilities, skills, knowledge and interests of the pedagogue only related to the implementation of the profession and professional activity.

For this he:

- ✓ tend to manage the process of creative research;
- ✓ one should remember that the effectiveness of creative research depends on the pedagogical, psychological and theoretical preparation of the teacher.

Summary

In the formation of professional competence, he strives for full professional formation, perceives pedagogical technological situations, including the ability to expand the scope of his professional interests, there is a demand for self-improvement. Most students develop a deep and persistent interest in professional knowledge, skills, abilities and abilities, and their manifestation.

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